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Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE RESEARCH TO ASSESS AN ONSET OF
AUTOIMMUNE PANCREATITIS (AIP) AMONG PATIENTS
WITH INVOLVEMENT OF ONE OR MULTIPLE BODY
ORGANS**¹Dr. Umar Saleem, ²Dr. Amna Rukhsar, ²Dr. Aleena Farooq¹Mayo Hospital, Lahore²Holy Family Hospital Rwp**Abstract**

Autoimmune pancreatitis refers to a diffused enlargement of the pancreas which narrows down the duct of the pancreas, fibrosis and lymphoplasmacytic infiltrations. The disease also attributes in the incidence of corticosteroid. In this research, we have studied a male patient of thirty-two years of age diagnosed with pancreatic head mass secondary obstructive jaundice and also secondary to biliary tract stricture along with unilateral exophthalmos. We raised the level of Serum immunoglobulin "G" with G-4 which is a high subclass immunoglobulin. Extraocular muscles unilateral thickness imaging was made possible through ophthalmological imaging. The better response of the patient was reported towards corticosteroid along with biliary strictures resolution, exophthalmos and pancreatic head mass.

Keywords: IgG4, Systemic Disease, Autoimmune Pancreatitis (AIP), Head Mass, Bile, Pancreas, Serum, Muscles, Biliary, Pathogenesis and Exophthalmos.

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INTRODUCTION:

Autoimmune pancreatitis (AIP) refers to a chronic pancreatitis form along with autoimmune pathogenesis. The association of the disease is made with attribution of associated organs such as gastrointestinal (GI) tract, biliary tract, kidneys and retroperitoneum [1]. AIP has two categories known as type-I and type-II. Old age patients with higher levels of IgG4 (Immunoglobulin G4) along with high relapse rate are of type-I; whereas, young patients having no high levels of IgG4 levels association and not experiencing higher relapse rate are of type-II [2]. Steroid management brought better response and also resolved the onset of swelling of the pancreas, involvement of the extrapancreatic organ and biliary strictures [3]. Few AIP cases have the involvement of one or two organs which is proved clinically; whereas, multiple organ involvement is also found among a few of the patients. In this research, we have studied a male patient of thirty-two years of age diagnosed with pancreatic head mass secondary obstructive jaundice and also secondary to biliary tract stricture along with unilateral exophthalmos. As we know, this case was unique in it holds AIP along with the involvement of extraocular muscle in our setting.

CASE REPORT:

In this research, we have studied a male patient of thirty-two years of age with asthma history diagnosed

from childhood along with weight loss (fifteen kilograms in last year), epigastric pain and jaundice. In the general physical examination, we came to know an onset of protuberant left eye which according to the patient was present since he was of twelve years of age. There was a mild abdominal tenderness as found in the assessment of the abdomen. The patient had already undergone an abdomen CT (Computed Topography) at another hospital which revealed CBD dilation (Common Bile Duct), dilation of IHD (Intra-Hepatic Duct) and pancreatic head mass. In the outcomes of earlier performed ERCP (Endoscopic Retrograde Cholangial-Pancreatography) revealed distal CBD stricture that was managed through the placement of the biliary stent. In the preceding six months duration there was a gradual reduction in the levels of bilirubin. MRCP (Magnetic Resonance Cholangial Pancreatography) performed at our hospital revealed pancreatic head mass (2.2 x 2.1) cm, distal pancreatic duct kinking and distal CBD stricture. According to clinical outcomes the CBC was normal, LFTs were deranged with total bilirubin, direct bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, AST (Aspartate Amino Transferase) and ALT (Alanine Amino Transferase) had respective values of 0.41 mg/dl, 0.20 mg/dl, 774 U/L, 346 U/L, 56 U/L and 51U/L as shown in Table – I.

Table – I: Clinical Outcomes

Clinical Outcomes (Unit)		Value
Total Bilirubin	mg/dl	0.41
Direct Bilirubin	mg/dl	0.2
Alkaline Phosphatase	U/L	774
Gamma Glutamyl Transpeptidase	U/L	346
AST (Aspartate amino Transferase)	U/L	56
ALT (Alanine Amino Transferase)	U/L	51

After that, we performed ERCP to measure cholestatic LFTs. We also removed the previously planted stent found that there were two irregular strictures on CBD respectively in distal CBD and a proximal portion that extends to right side IHD (one stricture each). We further placed two stents in right and left ductal system (one each). Colonoscopy and

Esophagogastroduodenoscopy revealed normal mucosa; whereas, in the histopathological outcomes we came to know about colonic biopsies and normal duodenal. Serological outcomes with the values of IgG and IgG4 along with respective reference range are given in Table – II.

Table – II: Serological Outcomes

Serological Outcomes	Value	Reference Range (gm/L)	
		From	To
IgG (G/L)	48.3	7.2	15.8
IgG4 (gm/L)	7.5	0.1	1.3

CA level (19 – 9) was normal with a value of (8.93 U/ml) as its regular value is under 33 U/ml. The anti-nuclear body was just positive (titer 1:40); whereas,

antibodies of anti-smooth muscle, anti-mitochondrial and anti-liver kidney microsomal were negative. No reaction was available in the viral serology of anti-

HCV and anti-HBsAg antibodies. The outcomes of Liver biopsy showed small expansion in the portal tracts along with fibrosis, lymphocytic infiltrate, mild focal cholestasis, occasional lobulitis foci and no necrosis piecemeal. The function of the thyroid was normal; whereas, level of anti-thyroid peroxidase antibody was abnormal (90.2 IU/ml) with a cut off value of less than (35 IU/ml). Normal radio contrast uptake was present in the scan of the Thyroid. ANCA (Anti-Neutrophil Cytoplasmic Antibodies) which include p-ANCA and c-ANCA were negative in this case. Orbital MRI revealed left-sided all extra-ocular muscles as thick, predominantly inferior rectus muscles and left lateral rectus having mild variations

in the retroorbital inflammation and mild proptosis having pseudotumor in the orbital inflammation as shown in Figure I and II. The chances of hepatobiliary malignancy were ruled out and a strong AIP diagnosis was important for a Type-I patient having orbital involvement and pancreatobiliary.

We started the therapy with a single dose of prednisone (1 mg/kg once per day), azathioprine (50 mg once in a day) and ursodeoxycholic acid (250 mg three times a day). An improvement in the LFTs was visible after six weeks follow-up. Figure III, IV and V show clear stricture resolution and ultrasonography shows the pancreatic head mass resolution. The left eye proptosis also improved significantly.

Figure – I: MRI Orbit reflecting left sided extraocular muscles thickness with mild inflammatory changes in retro-orbital

Figure – II: MRI Orbit reflecting left sided extraocular muscles with mild proptosis

Figure – III: MRCP imaging before steroid management reflecting strictures of distal and hilar CBD, pancreatic head mass at distal duct of the pancreas

Figure – IV: MRCP and ERCP imaging before steroid management reflecting strictures of proximal and distal CBD

Figure – V: MRCP and ERCP imaging after six months of the steroid management reflecting marked stricture improvement in distal and hilar CBD and distal duct of the pancreas

DISCUSSION:

The association of IgG4 with AIP forms a systemic disease which may involve one or multiple body organs. With the involvement of multiple organs, AIP becomes an important constituent which requires differential diagnostic approaches as it may include diverse entities like cholangitis, pancreatitis, pseudo orbital tumours and nephropathy. More research work may reveal the involvement of various other organs; AIP diagnosis includes five important

features which include Imaging, Histology, the involvement of related organs, Serology and steroid therapy response [3]. AIP patients show a significant response to steroids as it resolves affected mass lesions and jaundice. A typical dose of the steroid is prednisone (30 mg – 40 mg) per day for a period of four weeks following of reduced 5 mg tapering every week [4]. The recurrence rate was forty percent which was managed through immunosuppressants and steroids [5].

Clinical features described SIP type-I in our patient which also presented abdominal pain, obstructive jaundice and unilateral exophthalmos; imaging outcomes of the biliary strictures, pancreatic mass and pseudo orbital tumour. High levels of IgG & IgG4 serological outcomes and significant steroid response resolved biliary strictures, pancreatic mass and exophthalmos which were supported through diagnostic measures. However, there was no need for biliary stenting and ERCP for our patient. As AIP is a worldwide prevalent; a case of AIP with the involvement of lung, kidneys and inflammatory pseudotumors is also found in Japan [6]. Whereas, gastric involvement was seen in an American patient [7]. Effective diagnosis is possible through steroid effective response, serological markers and histological outcomes. In this research, we have studied a male patient of thirty-two years of age with asthma history diagnosed from childhood along with weight loss (fifteen kilograms in last year), epigastric pain and jaundice. A British AIP diagnosed patient reported the pericardial involvement along with pancreatic head mass, cholestatic jaundice and right heart failure [8]. In Japan, there was more frequent involvement of infraorbital nerve swelling among AIP patients [9]. In the UK, there was an involvement of the orbital mass in a child of five years of age because of orbital inflammation of IgG4 [10]. In this research, the patient presented the involvement of extra-ocular muscles with a pseudo inflammatory orbital tumour which caused the onset of exophthalmos. The patient's profile of thyroid was normal; whereas, level of anti-thyroid peroxidase antibody serum was elevated.

CONCLUSION:

Better outcomes are possible in AIP patients with immunosuppressants therapeutically interventions. Pancreas histological analysis is not possible because patients avoid experiencing invasive surgical and radiological interventions.

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